

The Encyclopaedia of Arabic Poetry by the Abu Dhabi Cultural Foundation, UAE

In 1997, the Abu Dhabi Cultural Foundation (<http://www.adach.ae>) began to develop an extremely useful multimedia Encyclopaedia of [Arabic] Poetry (*al-Mawsū‘a al-Shi‘riyya*). The first edition (published in 1998) was rather small and included only about 180,000 *bayts* (verses) by 88 poets, together with an electronic version of Ibn Manẓūr’s *Lisān al-‘Arab*. The second edition (published in 2001) was much more impressive, containing more than 1,800,000 *bayts* by more than 1,000 poets, as well as 46 additional sources with the character of reference works.

The third edition, which will be reviewed in detail in what follows, significantly surpasses the earlier versions: it contains 2,439,589 *bayts* by 2,300 poets, supplemented by 265 books on different aspects of Arabic language and literature (*al-lughā wa-l-adab*) and ten major Arabic dictionaries. Chronologically, it includes every piece of Arabic poetry from the pre-Islamic era until the present day (*kullu ma qīla min al-shi‘r al-‘arabī mundhu mā qabla l-islām wa-ḥattā l-‘aṣr al-ḥadīth*). More specifically, it includes everything for poets who died before 1953, and after that date, only the *dīwāns* of the most important poets (*aḥammu l-shu‘arā*). The entire program fits into a single CD.

As for the quality of the electronic texts, all the poems seem to have been meticulously reproduced: unlike in many other available databases, here the original formatting of the poetry is preserved, with all *bayts* split into two hemistichs, aligned in the traditional fashion, and fully vocalized. However, there are no indications in the database regarding the published sources from which the poems were taken. On the other hand, our fairly random attempts at comparing digital texts on the database with corresponding paper editions tend to convince us that the quality of digital reproduction of texts in this database is of a high level. Another 275 books — although similarly well-reproduced — also have no links to their respective paper editions.

In addition to a great number of poetical and prose texts, the program is fully packed with useful research and reference tools, such as a search engine with plenty of capabilities, a

meter analyzer, and audio recordings of selected poems performed by outstanding reciters of poetry (*nukhba min al-asātidha wa-l-fannānīn*). The developers also deserve praise for the comprehensive tables of statistical data on poets, poems, meters, verses and so on.

Bearing in mind the great number of texts and research tools that this database includes, as well as the high quality of the reproduction, this is an extremely valuable tool for any student of Arabic poetry, literature and language.

System requirements and program installation

The Encyclopaedia was tested on Windows XP. It is quite well-designed and stable, but not without some issues. Actually, the only major problem was installation: it is necessary to change localization settings, as otherwise the Arabic will appear unreadable and the program will continue to crash.

Windows XP. To change settings in XP: Go to “Start” → “Control Pane” → “Regional and Language Options” → [1] on the first Tab “Regional Options” choose Arabic (any country) in the “Standards and formats” section. [2] Then choose Tab “Advanced” and, in section “Language for non-Unicode programs”, choose Arabic (any country). [3] If Arabic is not available, go back to Tab “Languages” and in section “Supplemental language support” check “Install files for complex scripts and right-to-left languages.” Then choose Arabic as described above. You will need to reboot the computer.

NB: When you change language for non-Unicode programs, some symbols in some other non-Unicode programs (e.g. in German, French, Russian etc.) will appear unreadable. To use those programs you will need to change “Language for non-Unicode programs” back to the original language.

There are four different options for the amount of data to be copied to the hard drive, but even with the biggest available installation you will need to keep a CD in drive. This, however, can be overcome by making an image of the CD you own and running it in the virtual CD/DVD-Rom drive (e.g., by using “Daemon Tools,” a free utility).

Not really a problem, but an inconvenience nonetheless is the fact that the program is designed to work only in 800 x 600 resolution. This may prove inconvenient when it is used on monitors of high resolution, since everything will appear quite small.

The Encyclopaedia’s language of interface is Arabic only.

User's interface and basic capabilities

Opening the Encyclopaedia takes the user to the Main Window (see below), with two menus available. The vertical menu is the main menu, which provides access to the main features of the database; the horizontal one is the auxiliary menu, which provides access to different settings and technical functions.

Main menu (each major window, which can be accessed from the Main Menu, will be reviewed below in full detail):

Pic. P1 - Main Window

- *Ta'rīf* opens a window with a short introductory passage about the al-Mawsū'a l-Shi'riyya project, its history, and some major details regarding the current edition.
- *Shu'arā' wa-dawāwīn* opens a list of poets included in the database, with very short biographical entries. Each poet's page also shows the number of poems and poetic lines ascribed to him/her, and provides access to them. This page has convenient chronological and geographical filter options.

- *al-Qaṣā'id* displays the last open poem, which can be copied, printed and thoroughly studied with the set of built-in tools. The *al-Qaṣā'id* button is unavailable until any poem has been opened.
- *al-Istimā'* opens the section with audio recordings of selected poems, performed by outstanding poetry reciters (*nukhba min al-asātidha wa-l-fannānīn*).
- *al-Baḥth* opens the search window, where one can search texts of the database for a specific word or phrase; the search range can be specified in several different ways.
- *al-Maktaba* opens a section of the database with the most important Arabic sources on manifestations of language and literature (*majālī l-lughā wa-l-adab*); each source has an annotation and biographical details on its author.
- *al-Ma'ājim* opens a section of the database with the most important dictionaries of the Arabic language, each of which can be searched either for a particular word or a root.
- *al-'Arūḍ* opens a section with [1] basic information on the science of metrics (*'ilm al-'arūḍ*), including mnemonics for sixteen meters (pl. *buhūr*); [2] a meter analyzer; and [3] comprehensive statistics on meters in the history of Arabic poetry.
- *Ma'lūmāt* opens a window with detailed information on the contents of the database.
- *Pop-up Help Area*. Whenever the cursor hovers over a field or button, a short annotation pops up in this area. On the picture above, the cursor is hovering over the *Ma'lūmat* button (the cursor is invisible, but the name of the button differs in color from the other buttons) and there is a short annotation in the Help Area.

Auxiliary menu:

- *Ma'lūmāt 'an al-Mawsū'a* pops up a credits window with the names of scholars who have contributed to this project; and contact information (outdated).
- *Ikhtiyārāt* opens the user's bookmarks window.
- *Muwāṣafāt* opens display and printer settings.
- *Khurūj mu'aqqat* minimizes the program.

- *Khurūj* exits the program.

The *Shu‘arā’ wa-dawāwīn* window

Clicking the *Shu‘arā’ wa-dawāwīn* button opens a window where one can select or search for a certain poet, using a wide variety of options. Overall, the system of navigation for individual poets and their poems is very convenient and easy to use.

[Pic. P2-1]

- *List of Poets* displays the names of poets whose poems are available in the database. The list can be scrolled to a searched-for poet, or searched using the *Search Line*. The *List of Poets* can be filtered using available *Ranges* buttons:
 - *Chronological Ranges* buttons filter poets by epochs. For example, the *Qabla l-Islām* button displays only pre-Islamic poets; *al-Mukhadramīn* displays those who lived both in the *Jāhiliyya* and in the time of Islām; *al-*

Islāmī display those who lived in the time of [early] Islām; *al-Umawī* displays those who lived under the Umayyad Caliphate, *al-‘Uthmānī* displays poets of the Ottoman Empire, *al-Ḥadīth* — modern poets; and so on. *Kullu l-‘uṣūr* displays poets from all periods. (*al-‘Uthmānī* and *al-Ḥadīth* can be combined with *Geographical Ranges*)

- *Geographical Ranges* filters poets by regions, e.g., *al-Urdunn* displays Jordanian poets, *Miṣr* displays Egyptian ones and so on. *Kullu l-buldān* displays poets from all Arabic-speaking regions of the Islamic world.
 - *Gender Range* filters poets by gender and allows displaying either male or female poets, or both.
 - *Statistics For The Selected Range* displays the number of poets (*al-‘adad*), poems (*al-qaṣā’id*) and verses (*al-abyāt*).
- *Selected Poet’s Bio*: when a certain poet is selected, his/her short biographical entry is displayed on the left: full name, dates of birth and death, portrait (if one exists).
 - *Selected Poet’s Basic Statistics* is displayed below the biographical entry. This shows the number of poems and verses included in the database and the epoch to which the person belongs.
 - *Poems* button (*al-Qaṣā’id*): this opens a list of the selected poet’s poems.

Above in Pic. P2-1, the poets are filtered with the *al-Ḥadīth* and *Lubnān* options (Modern [Poets] and Lebanon). *Statistics for the Selected Range* shows that there are 47 poets (46 male poets and one female), 9,784 poems and 139,260 verses found for this search range. Jibrān Khalīl Jibrān (1300-1349 A.H./1883-1931 A.D.) is selected in the filtered list of poets and his biographical entry is displayed on the left. Below, the *Selected Poet’s Basic Statistics* show that there are 50 poems and 415 verses available, and that Jibrān belongs to the modern period.

Clicking the *Poems* button (*al-Qaṣā’id*) takes the user to the list of Jibrān Khalīl Jibrān’s poems (see Pic. P2-2). The right part remains the same as in the previous window, but the left part — in which the poet’s biography was displayed — now changes into a *Poem Details* table with the following columns:

1. *al-Maṭlaʿ* – the poems' opening verses.
2. *al-Abyāt* – the number of verses in each poem.
3. *al-Qāfiya* – the rhyme of each poem.
4. *al-Baḥr* – the meter of each poem.

Pic. P2-2 - Shu'arā' wa-dawāwīn

Poems Details

البحر	القافية	الأبيات	المطلع
موشح	ب	19	في سكون الليل لما تنتهي
مجزوء الرمل	ب	6	ليس في الغابات عدل
مجزوء الرمل	ب	6	ليس في الغابات عدل
مجزوء الرمل	ت	20	اعطني الناي وعن
مجزوء الرمل	ح	6	ليس في الغابات دين
الرمل	ح	30	كان لي بالامس قلب فقضى
مجزوء الرمل	د	12	ايها الشحرور عرد
الرمل	د	20	في ظلام الليل يمشى ميطنا
مجزوء الرمل	د	6	لم اجد في الغاب فرقا
البيسط	ر	4	وما السعادة في الدنيا سوى شبح
البيسط	ر	5	واللطف في الناس اصداف وان نعمت
البيسط	ر	4	فان لقيت مجبا هائما كلفا
البيسط	ر	7	وغاية الروح طي الروح قد خفيت
البيسط	ر	6	وقل في الارض من يرضى الحياة كما

Meter Statistics

Poet's Statistics

Navigation Options

العدد	القائد	الأبيات
47	9784	139260

مجموع القصائد: 50
مجموع الأبيات: 415

[Pic. P2-2]

Data in this table can be sorted (in descending order) by any one of these four columns. Sorting affects the availability of the Navigation Options, which are as follows:

5. 'Arḍ al-qaṣīda opens the selected poem (see *al-Qaṣā'id* section).
6. These alphabetic buttons bring the user to the first item in the *Poems Details* table, which begins with the selected letter. This applies only to a field by which the table is

sorted. For instance, if a table is sorted according to rhyme, then clicking the *Bā'* button will highlight the first item among all poems rhymed in *Bā'*.

7. *al-Buḥūr al-Shi'riyya* is available only when the table is sorted according to meter.

Selecting a certain meter will highlight the first poem within this meter range.

The *Meter Statistics* button (*Iḥṣā'iyyāt al-'arūd*) opens a chart which displays what metres were used by a selected poet and how many poems and verses s/**he composed in this meter**. Thus, Jibrān Khalīl Jibrān's preferred meters were *raml* (23 poems and 224 verses) and *basīṭ* (18 and 81, respectively).

The *al-Qaṣā'id* window

Clicking the *al-Qaṣā'id* button opens the last poem viewed. The top of the screen provides basic information about the poem: *Poet's Name* (Zuhayr b. Abī Sulmā), *Meter of a Poem* (*ṭawīl*), and *Number of Verses in a Poem* (59 verses). The poem itself follows below: each verse is numbered and the *Current Verse* is highlighted with a different color. On the left side of the screen one can find the Navigation pane, which allows the user to browse the open poem by verse and/or page, as well as to get to its beginning or end.

On the bottom of the screen one can find a toolbar:

- The *Commentary on The Verse* button (*Sharḥ*) opens a *Sharḥ al-bayt* window with detailed commentary on the *Current Verse*. This function is available only for major poems.
- The *Bookmark* button (*'Alāma*) bookmarks the *Current Verse*. Bookmarks can be accessed from the *Ikhtiyārāt* window (see below).
- The *Comment* button (*Ta'qīb*) opens a pop-up window into which notes can be typed. Comments can be accessed from *Ikhtiyārāt* window (see below).
- The *Print* button (*Ṭibā'a*) sends the current page to a printer. The printer can be selected/changed in the *Muwāṣafāt* window (see below). Depending on what soft- and hardware is installed in the host computer, the current page of the poem can be printed out or saved into available file formats (such as PDF).
- The *Copy* button (*Naskh*) copies the *Current Verse* into the computer's memory. After that, the verse can be pasted into any text file.

- The *Dictionaries* button (*al-Muʿjam*) changes the mouse cursor into a question mark. After this, clicking on any word in a poem will open the Dictionaries section (*al-Maʿajim*) of the database (for full details on this, see the relevant section below), where the meaning of the word in question and examples of its usage can be checked in any of ten available dictionaries. Click the *al-Qaṣāʾid* button in the main menu to return to the poem.

[Pic. P3]

The *al-Istimāʿ* window

Clicking the *al-Istimāʿ* button opens audio samples section of the database, which consists of three major sections: [I] *al-Muʿallaqāt al-ʿashr*, ten *qaṣīdas* recognized as classical masterpiece; [II] *Min shiʿr Abī Ṭayyib al-Mutanabbī*, a selection of 48 poems of al-Mutanabbī; and [III] *Mukhtārāt*

munawwa'a, six poems by Ibn Zurayq al-Baghdādī, Abū Nuwās, *al-imām* al-Shāfi'ī, al-Ḥallāj and al-Ma'arrī.

Materials of each section are arranged in tables: (1) *al-Unwān*, titles of poems; (2) *al-Ilqā'*, names of reciters; (3) *al-Abyāt*, the number of verses; and (4) *al-Mudda l-zamaniyya*, duration of the recording.

After a poem is selected, recitation starts automatically and the text of the poem is displayed in the *Recited Poem* section of the window, with the following information: (5) poet's name; (6) reciter's name; (7) volume control; (8) text of the recited verse; (9) ordinal number of the recited verse; (10) playback buttons. Poems are displayed verse by verse and synchronized with recitation; one can pause/stop recitation at any moment and move forward or backward with the playback buttons (10).

The *al-Baḥth* window

Clicking the *al-Baḥth* button opens a search window where one can search the entire database for a particular word or words, which should be entered into the *Main Search Line* (*al-Baḥth* 'an...).

[Pic. P5 *al-Baḥth*]

Search Ranges. A search can be conducted either in poems (*al-dawāwīn al-shi'riyya*) or in the auxiliary library of 265 sources on language and literature (*al-Maktaba*). *Search Ranges* can also be narrowed down by specifying epoch, region and gender.

Search Results are displayed in two columns, *Poets* on the right and *Verses* on the left. The *Secondary Search Line* can be used to find a particular poet in *Search results*, if their number is too big. When any poet is selected in *Search Results*, verses from his poems which contain the searched-for word(s), are displayed in the left column. The searched-for words appear in red.

Search Results Statistics are displayed under the two columns of Search Results: (1) Total number of poets; (2) Total number of words found; (3) Total number of words found in the poems of a selected poet.

Findings can be viewed either by clicking (4) the *al-Shā'ir* button in order to view a biographical sketch of a selected poet, or (5) the *al-Dhahāb ilā l-qaṣīda* button in order to view a selected poem (see the *al-Qaṣā'id* section).

In *Pic. P5* you can see that we have searched for the word *al-dunyā* in *Poems*. Since this is a common word, we have used the *Secondary Search Line* to find a particular poet, in this case Ibn Sīnā. The Search Results Statistics show that the total number of poets who use this word is 749; that it occurs a total of 9,994 times; and that in Ibn Sīnā's poems it occurs eight times.

The *al-Maktaba* window

Clicking the *al-Maktaba* button opens the database's library section, which consists of 265 books on different aspects of Arabic language and literature (*al-lughā wa-l-adab*).

Pic. P6.1 - al-Maktaba

The screenshot displays the 'الموسوعة الشعرية' (The Arabic Encyclopedia of Poetry) website. At the top, there are navigation links: 'مواصفات', 'خروج', 'خروج', 'خروج', 'مواصفات', 'خروج', 'خروج', 'خروج'. The main content area features a table with the following columns: 'العنوان', 'المؤلف', 'الصفحات', and 'الأبيات'. Below the table, there are two detailed views: 'Author's Bio' (الصولي) and 'Annotation to a Book' (أخبار أبي تمام). A 'Statistics' box shows the total count of books (265), pages (346,304), and verses (833,291). A callout 'Open a Book' points to a button at the bottom of the annotation view.

العنوان	المؤلف	الصفحات	الأبيات
نهاية الأرب في فنون الأدب	النويري	19893	16593
نور القيس	الحافظ اليعقوبي	712	2046
هواتف الجنان	الخرائطي	104	132
وصايا الملوك	دعبل الخزاعي	219	897
وصف المطر والسحاب		50	6
وفيات الأعيان وأنباء		860	860
بتيمة الدهر في ش	أبو منصور	25774	25774
العدد	المجموع	346304	833291

Statistics: 265 books, 346,304 pages, 833,291 verses.

[Pic. P6.1 - al-Maktaba]

All books are presented in a table with the following columns: *Titles* displays titles of books; *Author's Names* displays their respective authors; *Number of Pages* displays the number of digital pages for each book; *Number of Verses* displays the number of lines of poetry contained in a book. Below the table there is a Statistics line, which displays the total numbers of books (265), pages (346,304) and verses (833,291). For the full list of sources included in the database, see URL... The lower part of the screen contains a short biographical sketch of the author of a selected book (*Author's Bio*) and a short annotation to a selected book (*Annotation to a Book*). The *Open a Book* button takes the user to a selected book (see Pic P6.2).

[Pic. P6.2 - al-Maktaba]

On this screen, which is similar in its reading mode to the *al-Turāth* databases, the user can work directly with books. On the top of the screen we find there the *Title of a Book* (here, *al-Laṭā'if*) and the *Name of an Author* (here, *Ibn al-Jawzī*). On the right, we find a column of buttons:

- The *List of Books* (*Qā'imāt al-kutub*) button will take the user back to the previous screen, which shows the entire list of sources.
- *About a Book* (*Ta'rīf al-kitāb*) and *Author's Bio* (*Tarjamat al-mu'allif*) will display an annotation to a book and a biographical sketch of its author, respectively (a second click will take the user back to the book).
- *TOC of a Book* (*al-Fihrist*) opens the Table of Contents for an open book, which allows the user to navigate within the book. A book can also be browsed page by page using the Navigation Pane in the bottom left corner of the screen.

- The *Print* button (*Ṭibā'a*) sends the current page to a printer. The printer can be selected/changed in *Muwāṣafāt* window (see below). Depending on what soft- and hardware is installed on the host computer, the current page of the poem can be printed out or saved into available file formats (such as PDF).
- The *Copy* button (*Naskh*) copies the current page into computer's memory. After that, the verse can be pasted into any text file.
- The *Bookmark* button (*'Alāma*) bookmarks the *Current Verse*. Bookmarks can be accessed from the *Ikhtiyārāt* window (see below).
- The *Comment* button (*Ta'qīb*) opens a pop-up window, into which notes can be typed. Comments can be accessed from the *Ikhtiyārāt* window (see below).
- The *Dictionaries* button (*al-Mu'jam*) changes the mouse cursor into a question mark. After that, clicking on any word in a poem will open the Dictionaries section (*al-Ma'ājim*) of the database (for full details, see relevant section below), where the meaning of the word in question and examples of its usage can be checked in any of ten available dictionaries. Click the *al-Maktaba* button to continue reading the book.

The *al-Ma'ājim* window

The *al-Ma'ājim* section contains ten major dictionaries of the Arabic language, which are as follows:

1. *Asās al-balāgha* of al-Zamakhsharī (467-538 A.H./1074-1143 A.D.);
2. *Al-Ṣiḥāḥ* of al-Jawharī (d. 393 A.H./1003 A.D.);
3. ... etc.

There are two ways to get to this section of the database. One is to click the *al-Ma'ājim* button on the far-right pane of buttons: this will take user to a screen very similar to that of *al-Maktaba*, where one can read annotations to every dictionary and biographical sketches of their compilers. The second way is to use the *Dictionaries* button (*al-Mu'jam*), while the user is in

the *al-Qaṣā'id* or *al-Maktaba* section. This second way takes the user directly to entries for a searched-for word.

There are two ways of searching for a word. The first way is to search for a root (see Pic. P7.1), and the second way is to search for a particular word (see Pic. P7.2).

[Pic. P7.1 – al-Ma'ajim]

In the *Root Search* window (Pic. P7.1), one can select a dictionary in the *Dictionaries* pane, and then search for a desired root in two different ways. The first is to use *Root Search* to type in a searched-for root. The second is to browse a selected dictionary for a desired root by scrolling *Available Roots*. Here one can use the *Alphabet Pane* to limit the number of roots by their first letter: for instance, the number of roots beginning with *kāf* in the *Lisān al-'arab* is 400. *Root Statistics* will automatically display the number of available roots, and here one can check available options to obtain a statistical overview of trilateral (*thulāthī*), quadrilateral (*rubā'ī*) and multi-literal (*mazīd*) roots.

On the bottom of the screen one can find familiar *Functional Buttons* that are available in other sections of the database. Click the *Word Search* button to get to the *Word Search* window.

[Pic. P7.1 - al-Ma'ajim]

Here, in the *Search Line*, one can type in a searched-for word (one also needs to select a dictionary in *Dictionaries*, which will then be searched for the desired word). Click the *Search* button to start searching; the search results will be highlighted with a different color. Search results can be viewed by root entries: select a desired root in *Root Entries* to view search results in a particular root entry.

Click the *Root Search* button (*al-Judhūr*) to return to the *Root Search* window.

The *al-‘Arūḍ* window

This section of the database contains three sub-sections. The first sub-section, *Ma‘lūmat ‘amma* (Pic. P8.1), contains a very basic introduction into the *‘ilm al-‘arūḍ* (science of metrics/prosody) and mnemonics for 16 different meters of Arabic poetry.

Pic. P8.1 - *al-‘Arūḍ*

Basic Introduction Into the Arabic Science of Meters

علم العروض

كان الخليل بن أحمد قد بنى علم العروض على تشبيه بيت الشعر بيت الخيمة (الخيمة) واستعار من أدوات بناء الخيمة مصطلحات لبناء البيت الشعري، وجعل حروف البيت تنقسم إلى قسمين، الأول: الأسياب أي: الجبال، وثالث السيب من حرفين، والثاني: الأوتاد، وتؤلف من ثلاثة حروف، ثانياً أو ثالثاً ساكن، وجعل الأوتاد معصومة عن الجوارات، لأن وتد الخيمة إذا كسر انهدم جانب من الخيمة، وقسم الأسياب إلى قسمين (أوائل وثوان) وأوضح أن الجواز لا يقع إلا على التواني، عدا التواني التي يسبب سقوطها وتوالي خمس حركات، وبين أن هذه التواني إذا كانت متحركة فإن الجواز فيها تنسكين الحركة، وإذا كانت ساكنة فالجواز إسقاطها، وهو يسمى ما يطرأ على الأسياب من الجوارات بالزخافات، وهي نوعان: (مفردة: وهي تنقسم إلى مفردة واحدة ومفردة مزدوجة ما تقع على سيبين)، ولكل زخاف عنده اسم، وأكثر هذه الأسماء استعارها من تسميات الأوتاد، وهي الحروف الثلاثة الأولى من (مفاعيلن ومفاعيلن ومفعولن) أما فاعلاتن فوندتها (علا) في كل البحور إلا في البحر الخفيف والمجتث ليصبح (تفع).

Mnemonics for Meters

طويل تة دون البحور فضائلٌ فَعولُن مَفاعيلُن فَعولُن مَفاعيلُن
يشترط في عروضه: أي التفعيلة الأخيرة من الشطر الأول أن تكون مقبوضة، أي ساقطة الباء (مفاعيلن).
وهو أضخم بحور الشعر العربي آثاراً في الجاهلية والقرون الإسلامية الأولى، كقول الشاعر:
أيا منذر أقيبت فاستبق بعضنا حنانيك بعض الشر أهون من بعض

بحور الشعر

- بحر الطويل
- بحر المديد
- بحر البسيط
- بحر الوافر
- بحر الكامل
- بحر الهزج
- بحر الرجز
- بحر الرمل
- بحر السريع

Meters

[Pic. P8.1]

The second sub-section, *al-Taḥṭī al-‘arūḍī* (Pic. P8.2), is a very useful tool for determining the meter of particular lines of poetry. One must enter the first and second hemistichs separately in respective cells (*al-Shaṭr al-awwal* and *al-Shaṭr al-thānī*). Both lines must be completely vocalized, since otherwise the analyzer will not start (*Vocalization Buttons* can be used for entering short vowels). Once the user clicks the *Define Meter* button (*Taḥṭī al-bayt*), the analyzer will display the type of the metre in the *Meter Type* field (*al-Baḥr*), in this case *majzū‘ al-raml*. In the next two cells down — *‘Arūḍī Transcription* — both hemistichs will appear transcribed

according to the rules of *al-‘arūḍ* (prosody). In the in the lowest two cells (*Meter Formula*) the formula of the meter is displayed.

[Pic. P8.2]

The third sub-section, *Iḥṣā'iyāt 'an istikhdām al-buḥūr al-shi'riyya* (Pic. P8.3), is all about numbers. It provides exhaustive *Statistical Data* on the metrical preferences of Arab poets throughout the history of Arabic poetry. In its entirety, the statistical table (see *Totals* on Pic. P8.3) embraces 23 different meters, 117,081 poems and 1,480,402 verses. The *Statistical Data* in the table can be sorted by any of its fields: Meter (*al-Baḥr*), [Number of] Poets (*al-Shu'arā'*), [Number of] Poems (*al-Qaṣā'id*) and [Number of] Verses (*al-Abyāt*). *Statistical Data* can also be filtered by epochs (the 12 buttons in the *Chronological Ranges* pane).

Pic. P8.3 - al-'Arūḍ

الموسوعة الشعرية

معلومات عن الموسوعة | اختيارات | مواصفات | خروج مؤقت | خروج

معلومات عامة

Statistical Data

التقسيم العرضي

البيانات عن استخدام البحور الشعرية

Chronological Ranges

الأبيات	القصائد	الشعراء	البحر		
7045	635	213	الهمز	المخضرمين	قبل الإسلام
14723	1803	340	المجتث	الأموي	الإسلامي
25253	2604	472	المنسرح	العباسي	بين الدولتين
27341	1338	120	موشح	المغرب والأندلس	الفاطمي
49248	6217	668	السرير	المملوكي	الأيوبي
56476	4936	762	المتقارب	التحديث	العثماني
66428	4708	691	الرملي	كل العصور	
90971	5371	796	الرجز		
119056	10787	1136	الوافر		
130400	9548	834	الخفيف		
200711	16947	1186	البسيط		
316140	22123	1254	الكامل		
353475	27701	1572	الطويل		
1480402	117081	23	المجموع		

Totals

[Pic. P8.3]

The *Ma'lūmāt* window

With its three sub-sections, *Ma'lūmāt* provides detailed statistical information on the materials included in different sections of the database. Visually, these sections are very similar to the third sub-section of the *al-'Arūḍ* section.

The first sub-section, *al-Dawāwīn al-shī'riyya*, is a detailed table on poets and poems. The table consists of the following columns, any of which can be used to sort information: Name of a poet; year of birth; year of death; epoch to which a poet belongs; number of poems; number of verses. The representation of data in the table can be narrowed down by choosing a certain epoch and region (at the bottom of the screen). For years of birth and demise one can select either A.H., or A.D.

The second sub-section, *al-Maktaba*, is a detailed table on sources included in the Library section. This screen is basically the same as the main screen of the *al-Maktaba* section, with the exception of the *Author's Bio* and *Annotation to a Book*, which are lacking here. Similarly, the third section repeats the main screen of *al-Ma'ājim* section.